

Framework Evaluation Matrix

Evaluation Criteria: Experts assess each implementation phase using a 1–5 scale.

Score	Interpretation
1	Very Low
2	Low
3	Moderate
4	High
5	Very High

Implementation Phase	Infrastructure Requirement	Technical Feasibility	Cost Feasibility	Operational Efficiency	Overall Score
Phase 1 – Sensor Deployment	IoT Sensors and Gateways	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Phase 2 – Data Integration	Cloud Platform and Data Servers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Phase 3 – Predictive Maintenance	AI Analytics Software	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Phase 4 – Facility Dashboard	Monitoring and Visualisation Interface	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Phase 5 – Capacity Development	Training and Skills Development	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>